

Priming by low abiotic stress and DL- β -Aminobutyric acid compared to Acibenzolar-S- methyl to control of Tomato Crown and Root Rot Disease

Ragıp Soner Silme^{1*}

¹Center for Research and Practice in Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering,
Istanbul University, Fatih, Istanbul, Türkiye

*Corresponding author; email: rsoner@istanbul.edu.tr

ORCID: 0000-0001-6547-3747

Abstract

Crown and root rot disease caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *radicis-lycopersici* (FORL) is a destructive factor on the transplant and mature tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill) plants in greenhouses of Turkey. The synergistic effect of abiotic stress (100 mM NaCl) by known chemical defense inducers Acibenzolar-S- methyl (ASM) and DL- β -Aminobutyric Acid (BABA) on tomato plants was tested. The plants roots were immersed into 125, and 500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ BABA or plants foliages were separately sprayed by ASM (0.2 mg mL^{-1}) or BABA (125, 500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) before the plants were inoculated with 10^6 spor / ml fungal suspension by day 1 post treatment. Interestingly, BABA and ASM treatment combination led to negative effect on plant resistance though the plants sprayed with these compounds alone showed resistance to pathogen. Furthermore, in another study conducted on only by BABA and abiotic stress (foliar spray) resulted in remarkable plant disease resistance if the plants simultaneously were detached into BABA (125 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) solution. This combination caused a positive effect on plants, which was comparable with the plants detached into the highest BABA concentration at 500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Disease severity on plants on which abiotic stress and BABA combination used was also lower than the control and BABA-sprayed with 500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ plants alone by day 20 post inoculation. Therefore, synergistic effect between salt stress and BABA at lower concentrations suggests FORL resistance that could be associated with stress regulation effect of BABA.

Keywords: *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *radicis-lycopersici*, Acibenzolar-S- methyl, DL- β -Aminobutyric Acid, salt stress, priming

INTRODUCTION

Crown and root rot caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *radicis-lycopersici* (FORL) is most frequently observed in the Turkey's southwest tomato production areas. The fungus attacks tomato seedlings in the field. Acibenzolar-S-methyl (ASM), also known as benzo-1,2,3-thiadiazole-7-carbothioic acid S-methyl ester or BTH, serves as a recognized functional analog of salicylic acid (SA), eliciting resistance in numerous plant species against a broad spectrum of plant pathogens, particularly under controlled conditions (Thakur and Sohal 2013, Walters et al. 2013). Numerous studies have illustrated the ability of ASM to trigger plant defenses associated with systemic acquired resistance (SAR) (Durrant & Dong 2004, Bektas & Eulgem 2015, Baysal 2015). Moreover, this compound is commonly employed to chemically induce SAR in plant model systems, thereby facilitating the elucidation of the molecular network underlying SAR (Wang et al. 2006).

DL- β -Aminobutyric acid (BABA), classified as a non-protein amino acid, possesses the capability to induce plants by the absence of expressed defences. However, plants in this state exhibit enhanced responsiveness, reacting more swiftly and/or robustly to subsequent attacks compared to plants that have not undergone prior stress.

The enhancement of resistance in plants mediated by BABA is referred as the primed state. Priming entails the transition of plants into an alarmed state of defence alertness, resulting in an enhancement of their defensive capabilities (Conrath et al. 2002, 2006). Priming offers an economical and effective defense against plant diseases, especially in areas experiencing considerable disease pressure (van Hulst et al. 2006). BABA has the capability to provide defence against a wide range of both biotic and abiotic stresses, including *Peronospora parasitica* in *Arabidopsis thaliana* L. (Zimmerli et al. 2000), *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* in *Cynara cardunculus* L. (Marcucci et al. 2010), and *Bremia lactucae* in *Lactuca sativa* L. (Cohen et al. 2010, 2011).

Plants have the ability to develop SAR, which prevents subsequent infection of healthy tissues from a broad range of pathogens. Salicylic acid is a signaling molecule frequently associated with the resistance to biotrophic pathogens (Dempsey et al. 1999), such as its role in the activation of ethylene and jasmonate pathways enhances resistance against necrotrophic fungi (Ton & Mauch-Mani 2004).

In the previous studies of Baysal et al. (2003, 2005a), the effect of BABA and ASM on tomato seedlings has been shown in the control of *Clavibacter michiganensis* ssp. *michiganensis*. Also, the control of *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tomato*, particularly, without losing the efficiency even the plants were subjected to abiotic stress though plants were treated much lower BABA concentration than tested before by positive effect of synergism between BABA and salt stress has also been reported (Baysal et al. 2007).

Plants have been observed to exhibit priming-like responses to abiotic stresses. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that pre-treating *Arabidopsis* plants with BABA effectively primes them for abiotic stresses like low temperatures, high temperatures, and elevated salt levels or drought conditions (Conrath et al. 2002). Defense response in plants can also be stimulated by abiotic stress (Yang et al. 2001), which is called as “primed state”, depending on physiological condition of plant (Conrath et al. 2006).

To the best of our knowledge, there is no information concerning the priming effect of abiotic stress and the synergistic action of BABA on tomato seedlings against FORL. Therefore, the impact of salt stress on both inoculated and uninoculated plants that were treated with BABA and ASM were examined. BABA doses determined by preliminary phenotypic experiments were also tested in the studies conducted with ASM that tested by abiotic stress.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material

Five week-old tomato seedlings (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill. cv. Ikram F1, Syngenta) with four fully expanded leaves were used for all experiments. The plants were grown in pots in a soil mix containing sand, perlite, and peat compost in the controlled atmosphere rooms at $25 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ with 68- 80% relative humidity (RH). The soil mix also contained a slow-release fertilizer (14-12-14, N-P-K). Natural light was supplemented by a single 1000-watt sodium vapour lamp during a 16 h photoperiod.

Fungal Pathogen and inoculation

Fungal FORL culture was obtained from Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University, Molecular Microbiology lab. The pathogen was grown on potato dextrose agar (PDA) at 25°C for 4 days and then transferred to autoclaved soil tubes. The fungus was allowed to grow for 5 days in the tubes, and then stored at 4°C. The isolate, recovered as needed from storage, was performed on PDA at 25°C for 4 days prior to inoculation of plants. All experiments were conducted at 25°C.

Pretreatment with ASM and BABA

ASM (Bion, Syngenta, Frankfurt, as 50% active ingredients in WP formulation) was dissolved in distilled water to obtain the concentration of 0.2 mg ml⁻¹ and then sprayed on whole seedlings (ca. 200 ml per seedling) according to Baysal et al. (2003). BABA was made up as aqueous solutions with a final concentration of 125, and 500 µg mL⁻¹. Twenty-four hours prior to inoculation either solution was drenched into pots or uniformly sprayed onto plant leaves that treatments were adjusted to experiment design. Control plants were sprayed with water as well (Baysal et al. 2007).

Salt stress induction

The plant roots, including the ones sprayed with BABA and ASM at different concentrations as well as controls, which were washed with water properly, and were detached into 100 mM NaCl solution were exposed to salinity stress for 10 min or sprayed onto leaves. The control plants which are (-) control were not exposed to salinity stress and watered with only tap water as mentioned in Baysal et al. (2007).

Effect of ASM and the different BABA concentrations with salt stress against FORL

Plants were sprayed with various concentrations of BABA alone or, and the plants were subjected to salt stress either by detaching their roots at their base with 100 mM NaCl for 10 min or spraying (ca. 100ul per leaf). The foliage of seedlings was drenched with (ca. 20 ml per plant) 125, 500 µg/ ml BABA alone, or in combination with salt stress (100 mM; by detaching of plant roots). Control plants were sprayed with water (ca. 200 µl per leaf), and seedlings were covered with plastic bags.

The plants were inoculated with the spor suspension as described in Vakalounakis & Fragkiadakis (1999) by day 1 post treatment. The level of resistance induced in seedlings against *FORL* was evaluated 4, 7 and 10 and 20 days after inoculation (dai) using a 0-3 arbitrary scale according to Vakalounakis & Fragkiadakis (1999). A mean disease severity index (DSI%) was calculated from each treatment by adding the ratings for the 36 plants (two replicates of 4 plants for each treatment) and expressing the value as a percentage using the formulas as follows: $DSI = [\sum(\text{rating no.} \times \text{no. of plants in rating}) \times 100] / (\text{total no. of plants} \times \text{highest rating})$, disease incidence = $[\sum (\text{number of plants having the same disease index}) \times (\text{disease index})] / \{(\text{number of all plants tested}) \times 4\} \times 100$.

Table 1. The treatments and application method used for pot experiments: various concentrations of BABA, ASM and abiotic stress (salt stress*). **S:** foliage spray **D:** detaching roots into solution.

BABA ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	S	D	ASM (0.2 mg mL^{-1})	S	D	FORL	Abiotic stress (100 mM NaCl)	S	D	Pot range numbers
500	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	1
-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	2
125	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	3
125	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	4
125	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	5
-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	6
500	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	7
500	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	8
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9

(Footnote: NaCl applied onto leaves or the roots were detached into solution alone showed highly toxic effect on tomato seedlings.)

Table 2. The treatments and application method used for pot experiments. Various concentrations of BABA and abiotic stress (salt stress*). **S:** foliage spray **D:** detaching roots into solution. BABA was applied at 24 h before inoculation and ASM was applied at 48 h before inoculation.

BABA ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	S	D	FORL	Abiotic stress (100 mM NaCl)	S	D	Pot numbers
-	-	-	+	-	-	-	1
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
125	-	+	+	+	+	-	3
500	+	-	+	-	-	-	4
500	-	+	+	-	-	-	5

(Footnote: NaCl treatments applied onto leaves or immersion alone showed highly toxic effect on tomato seedlings.)

Experimental design and statistical analyses

Each treatment involved four plants and four replicates were performed for the analysis. Differences between the mean values were assessed through two independent experiments, each with four replicates. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed, and Duncan's post hoc test was used to evaluate the differences among the treatments at $P < 0.05$ using SPSS-30.0 Software.

RESULTS

Comparison ASM with BABA in Abiotic Stress Condition against *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *radicis lycopersici*

Disease incidence (DI) was on plants showing crown root rot disease or healthy ones as well as with control shown in figure 1 according to pot range numbers, representing situation by nine different treatments. Low abiotic stress application onto leaves combined with detaching of plant roots into BABA solution had identical control effect on pathogen growth compared to ASM (0.2 mg mL^{-1}) and BABA ($500 \text{ }\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) treatments alone. BABA ($500 \text{ }\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and ASM spray onto leaves had positive effect on plant growth and control of FORL interestingly, which appeared on plant roots though BABA (by detaching into $500 \text{ }\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ solution) and ASM (spray) combination did not reduce pathogen growth when it was simultaneously applied. Therefore, further experiments were conducted in order to determine synergistic effect of salt stress combined with low doses BABA treatments in the sight of these previous findings.

Fig. 1 Disease incidences on the tomato seedlings observed in the pots during experiments at 15 days after inoculation. The values (standard deviations of 4 different samples) with the same letters represent values that are not significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test ($P < 0.05$).

Fig. 2. The growth of plants with various treatments indicated in Table 1. Each number was separately given that valid for each pot range according to different treatments tested that shown in Table 1.

The Effect of Low Dose BABA Combined with Abiotic Stress (Salt Stress) against *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *radicis lycopersici*

Experiments conducted in order to determine the synergism between low dose BABA and abiotic stress showed that nearly 5 fold lower BABA dose combined with abiotic stress resulted in identical effect, which were obtained when the plants were treated with BABA ($500 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) alone. This case was shown according to disease index values calculated in different period of disease progress (3- 20 dpi) in Fig. 3 and the growth of plants at 20 dpi in pots were given in Fig. 4. The treatments did not demonstrate any difference in the disease index by 4 dpi, but they were significantly lower than the control group. The most suppressive effect on the pathogen was provided with BABA at different concentrations ($125\text{-}500 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) combined with salt stress by 7 dpi. BABA spray at $500 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ showed a significant suppressive effect on disease progress of inoculated plants. Detaching roots into BABA solution ($125 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) with abiotic stress (salt spray) showed remarkable suppressive effect (Fig. 3) that also observed on plants treated with BABA ($500 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) alone either by spraying or detaching. Moreover, detaching of roots into NaCl (100 mM) solution led to decrease in plant pathogen resistance though same plants were simultaneously sprayed also with BABA ($125 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Disease index values of plants detached into BABA ($500 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and the ones treated with BABA ($125 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)-abiotic stress combination showed less than 10 % ratio. The similar suppression effect on pathogen growth was until 20 days post inoculation (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. The growth of plants which were exposed to 5 various treatments that indicated under the each pot range at 15 days after inoculation.

Fig. 4 Disease index on plants inoculated with FORL was expressed as the mean of two separate experiments (in each experiment 4 pots were pooled at every time point (3-20) at post inoculation period). The values with the same letters represent data that are not significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test ($P < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

Priming is considered a component of systemic immunity responses in plants; however, the precise mechanism(s) underlying priming remain incompletely understood (Conrath 2011). Previous studies have established that BABA is capable of inducing a wide array of defense mechanisms, which are contingent upon the specific type of pathogens and plants involved. BABA demonstrates the capacity to generate reactive oxygen species (resulting in hypersensitivity response) and enhances physical barriers through processes such as callose deposition and lignin accumulation in cell walls (Ton 2005, Hamiduzzaman et al. 2005, Ton & Mauch-Mani 2004). Another mechanism facilitated by BABA involves the alteration of biochemical responses to stress. For instance, BABA promotes the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites such as phenols, anthocyanin, and phytoalexins, while concurrently enhancing the activity of enzymes linked to active oxygen species, lignification, and plant secondary metabolism (Wu et al. 2010, Justyna & Ewa 2013, Barilli et al. 2010, Chamsai et al. 2004, Andreu et al. 2006, Olivieri et al. 2009, Slaughter et al. 2008). Moreover, the activation of defense genes and the accumulation of pathogenesis-related (PR) proteins implicated in antimicrobial activity have been observed in numerous BABA-treated plants, including tomato, peppers, potato, and rape (Cohen 1994, Hwang et al. 1997, Altamiranda et al. 2008, Vladimir et al. 2011). However, contrasting examples exist, with some studies indicating no accumulation of PR proteins following root application of BABA (Siegrist et al. 2000, Jakab et al. 2001).

Priming is increasingly recognized as a critical process in various forms of systemic plant immunity, including systemic acquired resistance (SAR) and induced systemic resistance (ISR) (Conrath 2011). In the present study, a practical and effective approach was suggested in controlling FORL by synergistic effect between salt stress and BABA on tomato. By resistance priming with synergistic effect of salt stress was more higher than BABA alone in pathogen challenge. This study showed to induce substantial levels of plant resistance in tomato plants, 125 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of BABA combined with salt stress (100 mM NaCl) could result in significantly reduced symptom development and FORL growth. In previous studies, BABA was shown to be resistance inducer on tomato and had been tested against fungal and bacterial pathogens (Cohen, 2002, Baysal et al. 2005a, 2005b).

The findings suggest that applying BABA alongside salt stress led to the activation of plant resistance when the plants were exposed to a pathogen. The potential signal released by the pathogen could be significant in initiating the plant's defense mechanisms. In this case salt stress shows a synergistic effect on BABA-treated plants' resistance and leads to an enhancer effect on BABA even though the concentration was lower than the most efficient level (500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Consequently, the activation of resistance could be linked to the impact of BABA on FORL, which could be connected to its influence on the pathways involved in pathogen defense and responses to abiotic stress.

In conclusion, this study indicates that applying BABA at reduced doses under salt stress conditions can enhance systemic resistance in tomato plants against FORL infection more effectively than BABA alone, even at just about a quarter of the optimal effective concentrations. Salt stress has a synergistic effect on increasing BABA's effect. Therefore, it can be suggested that if the pathogen attacks to plant root, plant subjects to stress by spraying onto leaves for obtaining synergism created by BABA and abiotic stress but if the pathogen attacks to foliage of plants (Baysal et al. 2007) vice

versa. On the other hand when the pathogen damage also resulted from ASM and BABA treatment together although plants were induced by two different chemical inducer, in some extent, it may also associated with mode of action coincidence of two different chemicals *in planta*. This results may be related two different SAR mechanism induced by BABA and ASM. In addition to studies expressed by BABA and salt stress combinations were also tested in grower condition in greenhouses in Fethiye provinces and these results were also confirmed and showed parralel results in practice. Furthermore, the lab studies carried out showed positive results of this combination in inducing resistance of tomato plants to root knot nematodes, *Meloidogyne incognita* (Devran & Baysal 2018).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author gratefully thank to Ömür Baysal Ph.D. for his insightful comments and suggestions.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

Altamiranda, E.A.G, Andreu, A.B., Daleo, G.R. & Olivieri, F.P. 2008. Effect of betaaminobutyric acid (BABA) on protection against *Phytophthora infestans* throughout the potato crop cycle. *Australasian Plant Pathology* 37:421–427. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AP08033>

Andreu, A.B., Guevara, M.G., Wolski, E.A., Daleol, G.R. & Caldiz, D.O. 2006. Enhancement of natural disease resistance in potatoes by chemicals. *Pest Management Science* 62:162–170. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.1142>

Barilli, E., Prats, E. & Rubiales, D. 2010. Benzothiadiazole and BABA improve resistance to *Uromyces pisi* (Pers.) Wint. in *Pisum sativum* L. with an enhancement of enzymatic activities and total phenolic content. *European Journal of Plant Pathology* 128:483–493. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-010-9678-x>

Baysal, Ö., Gürsoy, Y.Z, Örnek, H., Çetinel, B. & Teixeira da Silva, J.A. 2007. Enhanced systemic resistance to bacterial speck disease caused by *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tomato* by dl-β aminobutyric acid under salt stress. *Physiologia Plantarum* 129:493–506. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1399-3054.2006.00818.x>

Baysal, Ö., Gürsoy, Y.Z., Örnek, H. & Duru, A. 2005a. Induction of oxidants in tomato leaves treated with DL-β-Amino butyric acid (BABA) and infected with *Clavibacter michiganensis* ssp. *michiganensis*. *European Journal of Plant Pathology* 112:361–369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-005-6234-1>

Baysal, Ö. 2015. Host Resistance: SAR and ISR to Plant Pathogenic Bacteria. In: Rajesh Kannan, V. & Baştaş, K. K. (eds.). *Sustainable Approaches to Controlling Plant Pathogenic Bacteria*. CRC Press. p. 206–224. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1201/b18892-11>

- Baysal, Ö., Turgut, C. & Mao, G. 2005b. Acibenzolar-S-methyl induced resistance to *Phytophthora capsici* in pepper leaves. *Biologia plantarum* 49:599–604. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10535-005-0055-0>
- Bektas, Y. & Eulgem, T. 2015. Synthetic plant defense elicitors. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 5:804. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2014.00804>
- Can, C., Yücel, S., Korolev, N. & Katan, T. 2004. First report of fusarium crown and root rot of tomato caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *radicis-lycopersici* in Turkey. *Plant Pathology*, 53. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3059.2004.01087.x>
- Chamsai, J., Siegrist, J. & Buchenauer, H. 2004. Mode of action of the resistance inducing 3-aminobutyric acid in tomato roots against Fusarium wilt. *Zeitschrift Fur Pflanzenkrankheiten Und Pflanzenschutz-Journal of Plant Diseases and Protection* 111:273–291.
- Cohen, Y. 1994. 3-Aminobutyric acid induces systemic resistance against *Peronospora tabacina*. *Physiological and Molecular Plant Pathology* 44:273–288. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-5765\(05\)80030-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-5765(05)80030-X)
- Cohen, Y., Rubin, A.E. & Kilfin, G. 2010. Mechanisms of induced resistance in lettuce against *Bremia lactucae* by DL-beta-amino-butyric acid (BABA). *European Journal of Plant Pathology* 126:553–573. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-009-9564-6>
- Cohen, Y., Rubin, A.E. & Vaknin, M. 2011. Post infection application of DL-3- amino-butyric acid (BABA) induces multiple forms of resistance against *Bremia lactucae* in lettuce. *European Journal of Plant Pathology* 130:13–27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-010-9724-8>
- Cohen, Y.R. 2002. DL-β-Aminobutyric acid-induced resistance against plant pathogens. *Plant Disease* 86:448–457. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PDIS.2002.86.5.448>
- Conrath, U. 2011. Molecular aspects of defence priming. *Trends in Plant Science* 16:524–531. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2011.06.004>
- Conrath, U., Beckers, G.J., Flors, V., García-Agustín, P., Jakab, G., Mauch, F., Newman, M.A., Pieterse, C.M., Poinssot, B., Pozo, M.J., Pugin, A., Schaffrath, U., Ton, J., Wendehenne, D., Zimmerli, L. & Mauch-Mani, B. 2006. Priming: getting ready for battle. *Molecular plant-microbe interactions: MPMI* 19(10):1062–1071. <https://doi.org/10.1094/MPMI-19-1062>
- Conrath, U., Pieterse, C. M., & Mauch-Mani, B. 2002. Priming in plant-pathogen interactions. *Trends in plant science*, 7(5):210–216. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1360-1385\(02\)02244-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1360-1385(02)02244-6)
- Devran, Z. & Baysal, Ö. 2018. Induction of resistance to *Meloidogyne incognita* by DL-Beta amino butyric acid under salt stress condition. *Australasian Plant Disease Notes* 13:20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13314-018-0304-7>

- Durrant, W.E. & Dong, X. 2004. Systemic acquired resistance. Annual review of phytopathology 42:185–209. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.phyto.42.040803.140421>
- Hamiduzzaman, M.M., Jakab, G., Barnavon, L., Neuhaus, J.M. & Mauch-Mani, B. 2005. beta-Aminobutyric acid-induced resistance against downy mildew in grapevine acts through the potentiation of callose formation and jasmonic acid signaling. Molecular plant-microbe interactions: MPMI 18(8):819–829. <https://doi.org/10.1094/MPMI-18-0819>
- Hwang, B.K., Sunwoo, J.Y., Kim, Y.J. & Kim, B.S. 1997. Accumulation of beta-1,3-glucanase and chitinase isoforms, and salicylic acid in the DL-beta-amino-n butyric acid-induced resistance response of pepper stems to *Phytophthora capsici*. Physiological and Molecular Plant Pathology 51:305–322. <https://doi.org/10.1006/pmpp.1997.0119>
- Jakab, G., Cottier, V., Toquin, V. Rigoli, G., Zimmerli, L., Métraux, J-P. & Mauch-Mani, B. 2001. β -Aminobutyric Acid-induced Resistance in Plants. European Journal of Plant Pathology 107:29–37. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008730721037>
- Justyna, P.G. & Ewa, K. 2013. Induction of resistance against pathogens by β -aminobutyric acid. Acta Physiologiae Plantarum 35:1735–1748. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11738-013-1215-z>
- Marcucci, E., Aleandri, M.P., Chilosi, G., Magro, P. 2010. Induced Resistance by beta-Aminobutyric Acid in Artichoke against White Mould Caused by *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*. Journal of Phytopathology 158:659–667. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0434.2010.01677.x>
- Olivieri, F.P., Lobato, M.C., González Altamiranda, E., Daleo, G.R., Huarte, M., Guevara, M.G. & Andreu, A.B. 2009. BABA effects on the behaviour of potato cultivars infected by *Phytophthora infestans* and *Fusarium solani*. European Journal of Plant Pathology 123:47–56. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-008-9340-z>
- Siegrist, J., Orober, M. & Buchenauer, H. 2000. b-Aminobutyric acid-mediated enhancement of resistance in tobacco to tobacco mosaic virus depends on the accumulation of salicylic acid. Physiological and Molecular Plant Pathology 56:95–106. <https://doi.org/10.1006/pmpp.1999.0255>
- Slaughter, A.R., Hamiduzzaman, M.M., Gindro, K., Neuhaus, J-M. & Mauch-Mani, B. 2008. Beta-aminobutyric acid-induced resistance in grapevine against downy mildew: involvement of pterostilbene. European Journal of Plant Pathology 122:185–195. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8973-2_14
- Thakur, M. & Sohal, B.S. 2013. Role of elicitors in inducing resistance in plants against pathogen infection: a review. ISRN biochemistry 2013:762412. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/762412>

Ton, J. 2005. Dissecting the b-Aminobutyric Acid-Induced Priming Phenomenon in Arabidopsis. *The Plant Cell Online* 17:987–999. <https://doi.org/10.1105/tpc.104.029728>

Ton, J., & Mauch-Mani, B. 2004. Beta-amino-butyric acid-induced resistance against necrotrophic pathogens is based on ABA-dependent priming for callose. *The Plant journal: for cell and molecular biology* 38(1):119–130. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-313X.2004.02028.x>

Vakalounakis, D.J. & Fragkiadakis, G.A. (1999). Genetic diversity of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates from cucumber: differentiation by pathogenicity, vegetative compatibility, and RAPD fingerprinting. *Phytopathology*, 89(2):161–168. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO.1999.89.2.161>

van Hulst, M., Pelser, M., van Loon, L.C., Pieterse, C.M.J. & Ton, J. 2006. Costs and benefits of priming for defense in Arabidopsis. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 103:5602–5607. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0510213103>

Walters, D.R., Ratsep, J. & Havis, N.D. 2013. Controlling crop diseases using induced resistance: challenges for the future. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 64:1263–1280. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/ert026>

Wang, D., Amornsiripanitch, N. & Dong, X. 2006a. A genomic approach to identify regulatory nodes in the transcriptional network of systemic acquired resistance in plants. *PLOS Pathogens*. 2:e123. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.0020123>

Wu, C.C., Singh, P., Chen, M.C. & Zimmerli, L. 2010. L-Glutamine inhibits betaaminobutyric acid-induced stress resistance and priming in Arabidopsis. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 61:995–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erp363>

Yang, K.Y., Liu, Y. & Zhang, S. 2001. Activation of a mitogen-activated protein kinase pathway is involved in disease resistance in tobacco. *PNAS* 98:741–74. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.98.2.741>

Zimmerli, L., Jakab, G., Me'traux, J-P. & Mauch-Mani, B. 2000. Potentiation of pathogen-specific defense mechanisms in Arabidopsis by b-aminobutyric acid. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 97:12920–12925. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.230416897>